

Communiqué

A Publication of The Relationship Institute

Vol 1, Issue 3

therelationship.institute

In this issue:

28 December 2018

Three Identified and Critiqued Measures of Sexuality

By LauraMaery Gold, LMFT
Northcentral University

Abstract

Female Sexual Interest/Arousal Disorder (FSIAD), a condition described in the DSM-5, can be quantified with available psychometric tools. Three measures of FSIAD are compared. Conclusions are drawn as to their relative merits.

Keywords: Female Sexual Interest/Arousal Disorder (FSIAD), test instruments

Cite as:

Gold, L. (2018). Three identified and critiqued measures of sexuality. *Communiqué: The Relationship Institute*, 1(3), 1-5. (Original work published 2015.) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4672230>

Original work submitted to: School of Marriage and Family Therapy, Northcentral University, Course MFT 5106: Research Methods and Evidence-Based Practice, Dr. Mark White, September 16, 2015

Three Identified and Critiqued Measures of Sexuality

Female Sexual Interest/Arousal Disorder (FSIAD) describes the persistent or recurrent condition in women in which sexual arousal is unattainable or unsustainable through the completion of sexual activity. In the DSM-5 (APA, 2013), the disorder is coded 302.72 (F52.22). (Male arousal disorders are contemplated in other sections of the DSM-5, and are not the subject of this paper.)

Three measures of FSIAD are contemplated here. The measures under consideration were administered to individuals in widely disparate settings in the US and internationally. The three measures are the 19-item version of the Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-Female (SIDI-F) (Clayton et al., 2006), and the 19-item (Rosen et al., 2000) and six-item (Chedraui & Pérez-

López, 2015) versions of the Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI).

Measure for Critique 1

Name of measure:
Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-Female (SIDI-F).
Developer(s):
Clayton, A. H., Segraves, R. T., Leiblum, S., Basson, R., Pyke, R., Cotton, D., Lewis-D'Agostino, D., Evans, K. R., Sills, T. L., & Wunderlich, G. R.
Source reference:
https://doi.org/10.1080/00926230500442300

<p>Construct(s) assessed (e.g., depression, relationship satisfaction, stress):</p>	<p>women with HSDD, compared to those with no FSD. The respective Cohen's <i>d</i> for each instrument was measured at 5.12, 2.52, and 2.74. They found similar results for the same three measures between women found to have HSDD, compared to those found to have FOD. The magnitude of difference is indicated by respective Cohen's <i>d</i> of 2.4, 0.61, and 0.72. The writers found that the the SIDI-F measures HSDD symptom severity more specifically than either the FSFI or the CSFQ. Convergent Validity Area: In the area, researchers found a significantly high correlation between the total score on the SIDI-F and the total score on both the FSFI measure and the IVR-CSFQ measure. Divergent Validity Area: In this study, when researchers considered all women, SIDI-F scores showed an insignificant correlation with scores on the MAS (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 121-124).</p>
<p>In a study of women diagnosed with hypoactive sexual desire disorder (HSDD), researchers used the SIDI-F to measure the severity of symptoms (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 116).</p>	
<p>Method of administration:</p>	
<p>Researchers studied 90 women aged 18 to 61 in the mid-Atlantic and Midwest regions of the United States. The women were administered multiple test measures in an attempt to determine study reliability and validity. Measures included the 13-item Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-Female (SIDI-F), the 14-item Interactive Voice Response-Changes in Sexual Functioning Questionnaire (IVR-CSFQ), the 19-item Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI), and the 15-item Locke-Wallace Marital Adjustment Scale (MAS). Using DSM-IV-TR criteria (APA, 2000), clinicians with expertise and experience in diagnosing and treating female sexual dysfunction (FSD) used "semi-structured" interviews to categorize interviewees into three groups: female orgasmic disorder (FOD) (<i>n</i> = 24), HSDD (<i>n</i> = 31), or no subtype of FSD (<i>n</i> = 35) (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 118).</p>	
<p>Summary of reliability evidence:</p>	
<p>Researchers reported excellent internal consistency with the SIDI-F, which resulted in a Cronbach's <i>alpha</i> of 0.90. They found six items (Receptivity, Initiation, Desire-Frequency, Desire-Satisfaction, Desire-Distress, and Thoughts-Positive) had a high item-total correlation ($r \geq 0.7$). They reported than an additional four items had good item total correlations ($r > 0.5$). These items included Relationship-Sexual, Affection, Arousal-Ease, and Arousal-Continuation. One item was reported with an item-total correlation rated poor: the orgasm item ($r = 0.1$) (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 125).</p>	
<p>Summary of validity evidence:</p>	
<p>The researchers measured validity in three arenas: Discriminant Validity, Convergent Validity, and Divergent Validity. Discriminant Validity Area: The researchers found a much greater magnitude of difference in scores for the SIDI-F than with the FSFI or the CSFQ, for</p>	<p>Describe the characteristics of the participants used to develop measure:</p>
	<p>The study measured only participants who were in a "stable, monogamous, heterosexual relationship." Participants with significant relationship difficulties were excluded, as were participants taking medications known to induce sexual dysfunction and participants with major psychiatric disorders such as depression or schizophrenia (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 118).</p>
	<p>Provide a brief summary of how clinicians have used this measure in therapy:</p>
	<p>In a clinical setting, with female clients diagnosed with HSDD, therapists administer the SIDI-F tool to assess and quantify the severity of symptoms (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 125).</p>
	<p>Recommendations for effective clinical use:</p>
	<p>The researchers recommend using the SIDI-F in clinical settings for women diagnosed with HSDD because it is designed to be "a brief, comprehensive, easy-to-administer" measure designed specifically for quantifying <i>symptom severity</i> and <i>change in symptom severity over time</i> (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 127).</p>
	<p>With what populations has this measure been used with (either clinically or in research) (e.g., ages, genders, race/ethnicity)</p>
	<p>A follow-up study by Clayton et al. (2010), considered earlier SIDI-F-based studies with women in Europe and women in North</p>

<p>America. The research grouped women by menopausal status, rather than by age. At least 90 percent of the European women studied were White (and ethnicity on the other 10 percent was missing). Of the North American women studied, 82 percent were White, and 13 percent were Black. The remaining five percent were Asian and Hispanic (Clayton et al., 2010, p. 2192).</p>
<p>Provide a brief summary of how this measure has been used in research studies:</p>
<p>One European study of 254 women in 11 countries confirmed the reliability and validity of the SIDI-F (Nappi et al., 2008). More recently, a medical study of oxytocin on sexual function used the SIDI-F and other measures to compare the effects of oxytocin and placebos (Muin et al., 2015).</p>
<p>Provide a summary of the findings from a typical study that used this measure:</p>
<p>The significant findings from the first Clayton et al. (2006) study is that when sexual desire declines in women diagnosed with HSDD, it seems not to arise from “a general dissatisfaction” in the partner relationship, and that for this same cohort, there is a clear distinction between sexual problems in the relationship and general relationship problems (p. 127). The medical study of oxytocin and placebos discovered both were equally effective at increasing sexual functioning (Muin et al., 2015).</p>
<p>What future research is needed on this measure?</p>
<p>The researchers noted they were seeking “further validation” for the minor modifications they were making to their measurement (Clayton et al., 2006).</p>
<p>Overall impression of measure:</p>
<p>Because the SIDI-F “exhibited superior specificity” and “enhanced quantitative differentiation” than either the FSFI or the CSFQ – and because it is relatively brief to administer – the tool would likely be an effective way to assess and quantify female sexual dysfunction (Clayton et al., 2006, p. 127).</p>

Measures for Critique 2

<p>Name of measure:</p>
<p>Female Sexual Function Index (19-item and 6-item versions)</p>
<p>Developer(s):</p>
<p>Rosen, Brown, Heiman, Leiblum, Meston, Shabsigh, Ferguson, & D'Agostino; Chedraui & Pérez-López</p>
<p>Source references:</p>
<p>ISSN: 0092623X; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2015.07.005</p>
<p>Construct(s) assessed (e.g., depression, relationship satisfaction, stress):</p>
<p>female sexual dysfunction</p>
<p>Method of administration:</p>
<p>Both versions of the test are self-administered.</p>
<p>Summary of reliability evidence:</p>
<p>Researchers found high overall test-retest reliability coefficients in each of the individual domains. <i>R</i> values ranged from 0.79 to 0.86. They also observed high degrees of internal consistency. In this study, Cronbach's alpha values measured 0.82 and higher (Rosen et al., 2000, p. 191).</p>
<p>Summary of validity evidence:</p>
<p>Researchers assert the study demonstrated good construct validity, with mean difference scores between the FSAD and control groups that were “highly significant” for each of the domains ($p < \text{or} = 0.001$) (Rosen, et al, 2000, p. 191).</p>
<p>Describe the characteristics of the participants used to develop measure:</p>
<p>The researchers administered the original FSFI-19 at five research centers to 131 normal controls and 128 age-matched subjects with female sexual arousal disorder (FSAD) (Rosen, et al, 2000, p. 191).</p>
<p>Provide a brief summary of how clinicians have used this measure in therapy:</p>
<p>The original FSFI-19 was used to construct a rapid screening instrument (non time consuming) capable of providing a snapshot of sexual status in a clinical setting. The test is self-administered (Rosen, et al, 2000, p. 191). The shorter version was designed to shorten the</p>

time to completion to 2 minutes (Chedraui & Pérez-López, 2015, p. 4).
Recommendations for effective clinical use:
With younger (<65) populations of sexually active women, administration is straightforward. Both versions of the measure are self-administered. The French study, however, demonstrates that there are difficulties with older populations, inasmuch as test questions do not capture “the nature of sexual activity” (Dargis et al., 2012, p. 130).
With what populations has this measure been used (either clinically or in research) (e.g., ages, genders, race/ethnicity)
The full version was used to study Chinese cervical cancer patients (Liu et al., 2015), to study older (>65) French-speaking women (Dargis et al., 2012), and to study the impact of sexual function on the Egyptian victims of sexual violence (Mohammed & Hashish, 2015). The shorter version of the FSFI was used to study mid-aged Ecuadorian and Spanish women (Chedraui & Pérez-López, 2015), and sexually active Korean women (Lee et al., 2014).
Provide a brief summary of how this measure has been used in research studies:
Researchers have focused validations on clinical populations, where they used the questionnaire mainly to diagnose and screen for sexual dysfunction (Dargis et al., 2012). For the shorter measure, researchers selected the best combination of six items that best represent the original domains of the FSFI-19, selecting a single item for each domain. Hence, the FSFI-6 covered: desire, arousal, lubrication, orgasm, satisfaction, and pain, resulting in the six-item version of the Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI-6) (Chedraui & Pérez-López, 2015).
Provide a summary of the findings from a typical study that used this measure:
There is evidence of good psychometric properties in the Chinese version of the FSFI. Researchers assert the scale is a reliable and valid instrument that can be used with women with cervical cancer in China (Liu et al., 2015).
What future research is needed on this measure?
Future research is needed to confirm the instrument among a large sample of cervical

cancer patients across China (Liu et al., 2015). Extending the questionnaire to include a “broader spectrum” of sexual activity might better address the needs of elderly women (Dargis et al., 2012, p. 130).
Overall impression of measure:
Head-to-head comparisons of the SIDI-F and the FSFI demonstrate slightly higher reliability for the former, and so while the FSFI appears to be more broadly used by researchers, that usage may shift with awareness of the superior reliability of the SIDI-F.

References

American Psychiatric Association. (2000). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (4th ed., text rev.).

American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Sexual dysfunctions*. In *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders* (5th ed.). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9780890425596.125889>

Chedraui, P., & Pérez-López, F. R. (2015). Review: Assessing sexual problems in women at midlife using the short version of the Female Sexual Function Index. *Maturitas* [Article in Press]. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2015.07.005>

Clayton, A. H., Segraves, R. T., Leiblum, S., Basson, R., Pyke, R., Cotton, D., Lewis-D'Agostino, D., Evans, K. R., Sills, T. L., & Wunderlich, G. R. (2006). Reliability and validity of the Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-Female (SIDI-F), a scale designed to measure severity of female hypoactive sexual desire disorder. *Journal of Sex & Marital Therapy*, 32(2), 115-135. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00926230500442300>

Clayton, A. H., Segraves, R. T., Bakish, D., Goldmeier, D., Tignol, J., van Lunsen, R. H., Nappi R. E., Wunderlich, G., Kimura, T., Lewis-D'Agostino, D. J., & Pyke, R. (2010). Cutoff score of the Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-Female for diagnosis of hypoactive sexual desire disorder. *Journal of Women's Health* (15409996), 19(12), 2191-2195. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jwh.2010.1995>

Dargis, L., Trudel, G., Cadieux, J., Villeneuve, L., Prévaille, M., & Boyer, R. (2012). Validation of the Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI) and

- presentation of norms in older women. *Sexologies*, 21(3), 161-167.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sexol.2012.01.002>
- Lee, Y., Lim, M. C., Joo, J., Park, K., Lee, S., Seo, S., & ... Park, S. (2014). Development and validation of the Korean version of the Female Sexual Function Index-6 (FSFI-6K). *Yonsei Medical Journal*, 55(5), 1442-1446.
<https://doi.org/10.3349/ymj.2014.55.5.1442>
- Liu, H., Yu, J., Chen, Y., He, P., Zhou, L., Tang, X., Liu, X., Li, X., Wu, Y., & Wang, Y. (2015). Sexual function in cervical cancer patients: Psychometric properties and performance of a Chinese version of the Female Sexual Function Index. *European Journal of Oncology Nursing*,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejon.2015.06.007>
- Mohammed, G. F., & Hashish, R. K. (2015). Sexual violence against females and its impact on their sexual function. *Egyptian Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 596-102.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejfs.2014.08.004>
- Muin, D. A., Wolzt, M., Marculescu, R., Sheikh Rezaei, S., Salama, M., Fuchs, C., Luger, A., Bragagna, E., Litschauer, B., & Bayerle-Eder, M. (2015). Effect of long-term intranasal oxytocin on sexual dysfunction in premenopausal and postmenopausal women: a randomized trial. *Fertility and Sterility*, 104, 715-723.e4.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fertnstert.2015.06.010>
- Nappi, R., van Lunsen, R., Tignol, J., Goldmeier, D., Pyke, R., & Staehle, H. (2008). T09-P-10 Validation of the Sexual Interest and Desire Inventory-female (SID1-F) in European women. *Sexologies*, 17(Supplement 1), S135.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S1158-1360\(08\)72891-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1158-1360(08)72891-3)
- Rosen, R., Brown, C., Heiman, J., Leiblum, S., Meston, C., Shabsigh, R., Ferguson, D., & D'Agostino, R. J. (2000). The Female Sexual Function Index (FSFI): A multidimensional self-report instrument for the assessment of female sexual function. *Journal of Sex & Marital Therapy*, 26(2), 191-208.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/009262300278597>